

Living on the edge: Spatial patterns of human–brown bear conflicts and implications for adaptive management in southwestern Iran

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Received: 19 February 2026 / Revised: 16 April 2026 / Accepted: 29 April 2026 / Published online: 03 May 2026.

How to cite: Shahbazinesab, K., Ashrafzadeh, M., Ranjbar, N., Mohammadi, A. (2026). Living on the edge: Spatial patterns of human–brown bear conflicts and implications for adaptive management in southwestern Iran, *Journal of Wildlife and Biodiversity*, 10(1), 132-152. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20001197>

Abstract

Human–carnivore conflicts increasingly threaten large carnivores worldwide, and the brown bear (*Ursus arctos*) is no exception. In Iran, which hosts the southernmost extent of the species' global distribution, such conflicts have risen noticeably over the past decade, yet spatially explicit information remains limited. Here, we aimed to determine the most important areas of tension between local communities and brown bears within the southwestern Iran, Kohgiluyeh va Boyer-Ahmad Province. Our study included field surveys and 332 semi-structured interviews with residents. Subsequently, the kernel density estimation was utilized to analyze five conflict types: attacks on humans, livestock depredation, damage to fruit orchards and beehives, and roadkill incidents. Our mapping highlighted the eastern and northeastern parts of the study area as hotspots for all conflict types. The overlap of conflict hotspots with protected areas was significant: approximately half of human attacks and livestock depredation events, 34.7% of orchard damage sites, 63.6% of beehive damage sites, and about a quarter of high-risk roadkill segments fell inside or at the edges of protected areas. Conflicts were more frequent during late summer and early autumn, linked to the bears' hyperphagic phase and seasonal human activities such as fruit

harvesting and moving beehives into mountains. These trends show that conflicts don't happen at random; rather, they occur when bears grow accustomed to readily available anthropogenic resources, human land uses encroach on bear habitats, and natural food sources are depleted. The existing overlap between bear habitats and human livelihoods in protected areas indicates that current management strategies are not sufficient. Without site-specific adaptive measures such as electric fencing around orchards and apiaries, bear-proof enclosures, and community-based early warning systems, conflicts are likely to intensify, undermining both local tolerance and the long-term persistence of this threatened population.

Keywords: large carnivores, local communities, damages, adaptive management, protected areas.

Introduction

Conflict between humans and wildlife has existed for as long as people have lived on the planet (Lamarque et al., 2009) and is recognized as one of the primary threats and pivotal challenges to managing biodiversity (Dorresteyn et al., 2014). This problem is especially serious in rural areas and the boundaries of protected areas (Dickman et al., 2010; Manfredo & Dayer, 2004; Mohammadi et al., 2021; Sikdokur et al., 2024). Consequently, recognizing, managing, or mitigating conflict is regarded as one of the most important conservation measures (Ahmadi et al., 2012; Karanth et al., 2013; Lozano et al., 2019; Mohammadi et al., 2019). Rapid human population growth has intensified habitat fragmentation, frequently forcing wildlife into closer proximity to human settlements (Inskip & Zimmermann, 2009; Rezaei et al., 2022; Woodroffe, 2000). Beyond demographic pressures, several factors contribute significantly to these conflicts (Naderi et al., 2025), including land-use change (Almasieh & Mohammadi, 2025; Distefano, 2005) and extensive human encroachment—such as resource extraction and the depletion of natural food and water sources—which has reduced the availability of essential resources for wildlife (Distefano, 2005; Lamarque et al., 2009; Naughton et al., 1999). Additionally, prey depletion of carnivores continues to be a key factor in these interactions (Anderson & Pariela, 2005; Mishra, 1997; Mishra et al., 2003). Furthermore, there is competition with wild herbivores due to the expansion of livestock in wildlife habitats (Distefano, 2005; Mishra et al., 2003), alongside climate change (Distefano, 2005; Patterson et al., 2004; Rezaei et al., 2023) and the acclimatization of wildlife to anthropogenic food sources, particularly crops and livestock (Kellert, 1996; Mohammadi et al., 2019)—are the main causes of conflicts between humans and wildlife.

Because of a wide geographic range and generalist diet, the brown bear (*Ursus arctos*) is frequently used as a model species in studies of conflicts between humans and wildlife (Bombieri et al., 2019; Can et al., 2014). Complete spatial segregation is frequently difficult to maintain, even though

brown bears generally behave shyly and avoid confrontation with people (Bombieri et al., 2019). Global data highlights an increasing trend in bear attraction to anthropogenic food sources, leading to substantial economic losses and injuries (Ambarlı & Bilgin, 2008; Can et al., 2014). Additionally, negative interactions that compromise human safety and cause property damage have increased concurrently in areas where populations have recovered due to conservation efforts (Can & Togan, 2004; Karamanlidis et al. 2011; Rigg et al., 2011). As an example, interactions with Tibetan brown bears (*U. a. pruinosus*) in China represent some of the most prominent conflict cases globally (Dai et al., 2019a). According to Dai et al. 2019, the brown bear poses the greatest threat to human safety in the Sanjiangyuan region of China, with numerous reports of livestock predation and attacks on local communities (Dai et al., 2019; Worthy & Foggin, 2008). Beyond depredation, these bears frequently infringe upon residential areas, a behavior deemed "intolerable" by local communities (Dai et al., 2019b). By 2020, this species was responsible for about 42% of China's total economic costs resulting from damages caused by carnivores (Dai et al., 2020). Tangible damage to human assets such as crop raiding, livestock predation, and property destruction usually makes conflicts worse. Furthermore, the perceived risk and fear of attacks contribute to tension, even though actual predatory attacks remain exceedingly rare (Bombieri et al., 2019). According to studies, bears may venture far from their denning locations in search of garbage cans or other human food, which attracts them to populated areas. Studies indicate that bears may travel long distances from their denning sites to find garbage cans or other human food, which draws them toward settlements. Such foraging patterns lead to excessive proximity to humans, increasing the likelihood of chance encounters and subsequent injuries (Farhadinia et al., 2019; Parchizadeh & Belant, 2021).

Brown bears have experienced significant range contraction in the Middle East and are now mostly confined to small, fragmented populations in Iran, Iraq, and Turkey (Calvignac et al., 2009; McLellan et al., 2017). Iran is the southernmost extent of the species' global distribution (Mohammadi et al., 2021), where brown bears are members of a distinct mitochondrial lineage (Ashrafzadeh et al., 2018). Escalating human–brown bear conflicts in recent years have further complicated conservation efforts in western Iran. Strategic adaptive management and conservation measures must be put in place, due to the magnitude of economic losses and risks to human safety (Parchizadeh & Belant, 2021). The long-term viability of brown bear populations in this area could be seriously threatened if these interactions are not addressed (Qashqaei et al., 2014).

Consequently, developing effective mitigation requires accurate and reliable data on conflict incidents to identify conflict hotspots (Hipólito et al., 2020). Kohgiluyeh va Boyer-Ahmad province, located in southwestern Iran, encompasses critical brown bear habitats within the Central Zagros Mountains. In recent years, this area has recorded numerous conflict reports involving local communities. The present study aimed to identify conflict hotspots between brown bears and local communities—concerning both property damage and threats to human safety—across the province to support coexistence-oriented conservation strategies and adaptive management plans.

Martial and methods

Study Area

This study covered an area of about 16,264 km² in the southwestern part of Iran, including Kohgiluyeh va Boyer-Ahmad province (Fig. 1). It ranges in altitude from 500 to 4,409 meters above sea level. The Zagros Mountains, which dominate this region, extend parallel from northwest to southeast. Climatically, this region can be split into two distinct types: 1) The north and northeast, a cold region with an average annual rainfall of 600 to 800 mm; and 2) South and west, a tropical region with an average annual rainfall of 350 to 500 mm. The dominant vegetation in this province is Persian oak (*Quercus brantii*). The Persian leopard (*Panthera pardus*), striped hyena (*Hyaena hyaena*), and gray wolf (*Canis lupus*) are other large carnivores that coexist with brown bear. Conflict locations, including georeferenced locations of bear injuries to humans and damage to people's property in the study area are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Locations of interviews conducted with local communities, georeferenced sites of livestock predation and brown bear attacks on humans (human safety), areas of orchard and beehive damage, and mammalian roadkill incidents within the brown bear's habitat range

Data analyses

To identify high-risk zones of conflict between brown bears and human interests, data on attacks on human safety, livestock predation, and damage to anthropogenic food sources (orchards and beehives) were collected. Data collection was conducted through field surveys from Autumn 2021 to Autumn 2022, alongside semi-structured face-to-face interviews with 332 members of local communities—including orchardists, farmers, beekeepers, and pastoralists—who lived within and close to the brown bears' habitat range. Additionally, records from the Provincial Department of Environment were included. A total of 27 reports of human attacks, 31 cases of livestock predation, 124 incidents of orchard damage, and 33 cases of beehive damage were compiled, spanning the five years preceding the fieldwork. To guarantee accurate and trustworthy data, only reports that had undergone expert evaluation and field validation were included. Using ArcGIS 10.5, the Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) was used to identify conflict hotspots. By superimposing a grid

over the occurrence points, the KDE function computes a density surface and uses an ideal search radius to determine the risk intensity. The search radius (bandwidth) used in this study was 500 meters. A circular neighborhood is defined by the given radius for each observation point, and the density per unit area is computed. Each cell's final value is the sum of all overlapping circular surfaces, with points nearer the circle's center receiving higher weights (Xie and Yan 2013). This approach makes it easier to create adaptive management plans by identifying regions with the highest likelihood of risk. We evaluated the impact of bandwidth selection using three different values: 300 m, 500 m (our chosen value), and 800 m (Table 1). This sensitivity analysis was performed separately for each of the five conflict types. We used the default rule-of-thumb bandwidth calculated by ArcGIS's Kernel Density Estimation tool (based on Silverman, 1986), which produced an optimal value of approximately 480–520 m for our combined dataset. We rounded this to 500 m for practical reporting.

In order to identify potential roadkill hotspots for brown bears, 67 mammalian roadkill incidents within the bears' habitat range were documented through field survey reports already in existence and interviews with experts and environmental guards. Similarly, high-risk road sections for brown bears were mapped using the KDE tool in ArcGIS 10.5, offering a spatial foundation for coexistence-oriented conservation strategies.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

The total household membership of all interviewees comprised 1,716 individuals. A household size of six members was reported by the majority of respondents (26.8%), followed by five members (24.4%). About 87.9% of the participants were men and 12.1% were women. In terms of age distribution, the largest group (25.9%) was between the ages of 40 and 50, followed by those between the ages of 30 and 40 (25%), 50 and 60 (20.5%), 20 and 30 (17.2%), and over 60 (11.4%). The educational profile of the local communities was as follows: 34.6% had a high school diploma, 17.8% had a university degree, 16.6% had a middle school education, 12.5% were illiterate, 9.3% had basic literacy, and 9.0% had an elementary school education. Livelihood analysis revealed that 59.94% of respondents worked in agriculture, 53.1% in livestock farming, 47.3% in orcharding, 22.6% in shepherding, and 20.8% in beekeeping. Additionally, 43.7% reported involvement in alternative livelihoods, such as carpet weaving. Together, the interviewees oversaw over 1,800 beehives, 405 hectares of agricultural land, and about 186 hectares of orchards,

all of which are important anthropogenic food sources that may lead to conflict. In terms of livestock ownership, 26.5% of those surveyed had fewer than 50 head, 17.2% had between 50 and 100, 9.3% had between 100 and 200, and 0.9% had more than 200 head. The participants had about 170 herd dogs in total. Lastly, a high degree of proximity and the possibility of conflict incidents are indicated by nearly half of the respondents (49.7%) who reported having personally seen brown bears.

Conflict hotspots

The results of the sensitivity analysis for bandwidth selection based on three different values (300, 500, and 800 m) are shown in Table 1. The overall spatial pattern – i.e., the concentration of hotspots in the eastern and northeastern parts of the province– remained stable and consistent across all three bandwidths. Only the exact hotspot boundaries exhibited slight variation. This confirms the robustness of our main findings.

Table 1. Results of the sensitivity analysis to bandwidth selection

Bandwidth	Outcome
300 m	Hotspots became overly fragmented, appearing as very small and isolated clusters (often only 1–2 cells). This pattern is ecologically unrealistic and shows high variance with artificial artifacts.
500 m	Optimal bandwidth. Achieved the best balance between variance reduction and preservation of spatial detail. Clusters were ecologically meaningful and stable.
800 m	Excessive smoothing. Multiple distinct conflict zones (e.g., from different valleys) were incorrectly merged into a single cluster, introducing high bias.

According to the findings, the main conflict hotspots are concentrated in the eastern part of the study area, despite reports of brown bear attacks on humans occurring in a variety of habitats (Fig. 2). In the last five years, about 22.9% (n=76) of the local communities surveyed reported that they or their acquaintances had been attacked by a brown bear. Seasonally, spring accounted for 64.5% of these attacks, followed by summer (31.6%), fall (2.6%), and winter (1.3%). Overall, the results show that about half of the recorded attacks on human safety took place inside the borders of protected areas, especially Dena National Park and the Dena-ye Sharqi protected area.

The KDE results indicate that livestock predation by bears occurs in several parts of the province. However, eastern and northeastern regions of the study area are where the majority of these incidents and conflict hotspots are located (Fig. 3). Results show that 0.9% of the interviewees reported direct bear attacks on their own livestock. Additionally, 28 additional cases of livestock predation were compiled based on reports from environmental guards, experts, and local communities over the same period. Approximately 51.6% (n=31) of the livestock predation locations overlapped with the boundaries of protected areas, including Dena National Park, the Dena-ye Sharqi, Dena-ye Gharbi, and Sivak protected areas.

Figure 2. Conflict hotspots of brown bear attacks on humans, identified using KDE analysis.

Figure 3. Conflict hotspots of brown bear-inflicted livestock predation, identified using KDE analysis.

The results indicated that the eastern parts of the study area were conflict hotspots for brown bear damage to beehives and orchard crops (Figs. 4 and 5). A total of 98 respondents (29.5%) from local communities reported that bears had damaged their orchard products, involving 802 trees. Apple (31.6%), grape (22.8%), peach (16.1%), plum (9.3%), apricot (6.2%), and other fruit varieties (14.0%) were among the damaged anthropogenic food sources. Most of these damages occurred in the summer and early fall. Geographically, 34.7% of the orchard damage locations overlapped with a protected area. Another crucial anthropogenic food source, 243 beehives were damaged by bears according to 58 respondents (17.5%). Protected areas overlapped with about 63.6% of the beehive damage locations.

Figure 4. Conflict hotspots of brown bear-inflicted damage to fruit orchards (as anthropogenic food sources), identified using KDE analysis.

Figure 5. Conflict hotspots of brown bear-inflicted damage to beehives (as anthropogenic food sources), identified using KDE analysis.

Collision hotspots

The eastern and central parts were found to be the main conflict hotspots for brown bear-vehicle collisions and roadkill incidents (Fig. 6). Dena National Park, Dena-ye Sharqi and Sivak protected areas, and the Khorram-Naz prohibited hunting area were all considered critical hotspots. These high-risk areas are concentrated along major transit corridors, including the Pataveh–Dehdasht highway, the old Yasuj–Shiraz road (Vezg Pass), and the routes connecting Sisakht to Sarbaz, Yasuj to Sisakht, Gachsaran to Baba-Meydan, Dehdasht to Kalayeh, and Yasuj to Baba-Meydan. Findings indicate that approximately 25.4% of the identified probable accident and mortality locations overlap with the boundaries of protected areas.

Figure 6. Probable conflict hotspots for brown bear-vehicle collisions and roadkill incidents, identified using KDE analysis.

Discussion

Small and relatively isolated groups primarily restrict brown bear populations in the habitats of western Iran. Today, the conservation of these remaining populations depends on the effectiveness of management strategies. The conservation challenges in this area have become more complex recently due to an increase in human-wildlife conflicts between local communities and bears. The development of effective conservation strategies and adaptive management programs is imperative due to the complex interplay between the essential needs of brown bears and the livelihood needs of local communities. The present study focused on identifying the conflict hotspots between brown bears and local communities in Kohgiluyeh va Boyer-Ahmad Province using the KDE function.

Numerous studies highlight how wildlife is more prevalent near human settlements due to natural habitat fragmentation and human population growth (Khosravi et al., 2022; Naderi et al., 2024).

Bears have become more reliant on anthropogenic food sources as a result of widespread human interference with nature such as overexploitation and the depletion of food and water resources (Ashrafzadeh et al. 2023). Furthermore, the easy accessibility of these human-related food resources has drawn bears toward human settlements, intensifying the human-wildlife conflict (Mohammadi & Almasieh, 2022; Qashqaei et al., 2014; Shahbazinasab et al., 2023). Furthermore, a species distribution pattern is significantly influenced by the size of its home range (Sinclair, 2016). Brown bears can therefore travel great distances in pursuit of food due to their large home ranges (Mangipanea et al., 2018; Zarzo-Arias et al., 2019). Bear mortality has increased as a result of these conditions which have increased human-wildlife conflict (Penteriani et al., 2019; Zahoor et al., 2021; Nayeri et al., 2022). Brown bears have a comparatively high level of conflict with human societies because they are omnivores and share a dietary niche with humans (Madadi et al., 2020; Qashqaei et al., 2014). In Asian countries, the livelihoods of local communities play a significant role in the intensity of human-bear conflicts and are paramount to the acceptance of conservation strategies by these communities (Chauhan, 2003; Charoo et al., 2011; Bombieri et al., 2023).

Based on the findings, brown bears cause significant damage to human assets in Kohgiluyeh va Boyer-Ahmad province annually. The highest reported damage in the province occurs from late summer to early fall—corresponding to the bears' hyperphagia period—while the lowest coincides with their hibernation (Zarzo-Arias et al., 2021). In recent years, anthropogenic activities, including orcharding, animal husbandry, and beekeeping, have expanded considerably within and around brown bear habitats across the study area; even protected areas have not remained immune to this expansion. While reports of brown bear attacks on humans exist across various habitats, the majority of these incidents are concentrated in the eastern regions. Furthermore, most damage to anthropogenic food sources, such as livestock, orchard crops, and beehives, is centered in the eastern portion of the study area. According a recent study, these eastern areas of the central Zagros are the most suitable bear habitats (Ashrafzadeh et al., 2023), many of which coincide with areas that are already protected.

The results highlight that a significant percentage of bear-related injuries and property damages take place inside or close to protected areas. In other words, there is a substantial spatial overlap between conflict hotspots and the boundaries of protected areas and core brown bear habitats. Additionally, the majority of these damage incidents happen before and after hibernation. The

degree of damage varies by year, season, and bear population density. It is also impacted by the accessibility of anthropogenic food sources like beehives, livestock, and orchard products, as well as the availability of natural food resources and climate (Zarzo-Arias et al., 2021). Bears show less fear of humans during the hyperphagia phase prior to hibernation (to build up fat reserves) or right after (when suffering from severe nutritional deficiencies and weight loss), particularly when natural food is scarce. As a result, they easily penetrate orchards and other areas where humans predominate in quest of anthropogenic food sources (Marchini et al., 2019; Zarzo-Arias et al., 2021). During these times of transition to human resources, brown bears frequently leave their natural habitats, especially protected areas (Dai et al., 2019b).

Conversely, one of the main causes of increased human-wildlife conflict is the existence of local communities in and around core wildlife habitats, especially protected areas (Behmanesh et al., 2018; Khosravi & Sadeghi, 2022; Parchizadeh & Belant, 2021; Sıkdokur et al., 2024). The likelihood of unexpected encounters and ensuing conflicts is increased when more people enter these areas (Parchizadeh & Belant, 2021). The risk of encounters is further exacerbated in the study area by anthropogenic disturbances like the spring harvesting of aromatic and medicinal plants and the summer seasonal relocation of beehives to these habitats. Bears have a acute sense of smell, and when they smell humans from a distance they usually run away; but if they are startled up close they may act defensively. In fact, most bear attacks on people are essentially defensive in nature (Smith et al., 2005).

While conflicts in the study area are driven by concerns regarding potential injuries and damages to assets, the majority of conflict hotspots have historically arisen due to bear-inflicted damages to fruit orchards. Various studies corroborate that damage to fruit orchards (as a key anthropogenic food source) ranks highest among conflict-related losses (Hipólito et al., 2019). Consistent with previous research, the findings of this study confirm that brown bears extensively utilize orchard crops such as apples, grapes, apricots, and peaches (Fahimi & Yusefi, 2010; Khaleghizadeh & Khormali, 2005; Qashqaei et al., 2014; Soofi et al., 2018). In alignment with our findings, there are relatively few reports of brown bear attacks on livestock in Iran (e.g., Nezami, 2008). In contrast, for the Pyrenean brown bear population, livestock predation was the most prevalent form of damage during both the summer and autumn seasons (Zarzo-Arias et al., 2021).

Conclusion

This study provides the first spatially explicit assessment of human–brown bear conflict hotspots in Kohgiluyeh va Boyer-Ahmad province, southwestern Iran. By integrating field-verified conflict records with semi-structured interviews and KDE analysis, we identified that the eastern and northeastern parts of the province—particularly areas surrounding Dena National Park and the Dena-ye Sharqi protected area—consistently represent high-risk zones for attacks on humans, livestock depredation, damage to orchards and beehives, and bear-vehicle collisions. Notably, between one-third and two-thirds of all conflict incidents that were documented overlapped with the boundaries of protected areas, highlighting the fact that legally designated conservation zones do not inherently reduce negative interactions. Bear hyperphagia and the existence of local communities involved in horticulture, beekeeping, and the gathering of medicinal plants coincide with the seasonal peak of conflicts during the spring and summer suggesting a temporal and spatial convergence of resource needs. From a management standpoint, our results demonstrate the critical need to switch from reactive mitigation to proactive coexistence-focused strategies. The close spatial overlap between core brown bear habitats and livelihood activities—including orcharding, livestock grazing, and apiculture—implies that no single solution will be effective across all hotspots. Adaptive management plans, on the other hand, ought to integrate site-specific interventions (e.g., bear-proof waste management, electric fencing around orchards, and apiaries and livestock guard dogs) with more comprehensive land-use planning that takes bear movement corridors into consideration (Mohammadi et al. 2021), as well as seasonal resource bottlenecks. Improving local community engagement and benefit-sharing mechanisms is just as important as bolstering law enforcement, as evidenced by the high percentage of conflict incidents within protected areas. Without such integrated efforts, the escalating trend of human–brown bear conflicts will likely continue undermining both bear conservation and local livelihoods in this southernmost part of the species’ global range.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to express their sincere gratitude to the experts and environmental guards of the Kohgiluyeh va Boyer-Ahmad Department of Environment (DoE) for their invaluable assistance and cooperation during the field surveys of this study.

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